

(1) Title and Details

(A) Title

Faris-Newton Classical Mechanics

(B) Author Information

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(2) Short Summary

In this article I introduced some new physical quantities named as movements then I give their proof by deriving it from motion equation. After which I wrote Faris-Newton Without Mass motion Equation which converts to Faris-Newton With Mass Motion Laws Equation which converts to Faris-Newton Force Laws Equation which converts to Faris-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation. In this way I form Motion Laws Equation and Gravitation Force Laws Equation which forms the foundation of Faris-Newton Classical Mechanics.

(3) Keywords

(1) N Integrals of Position Function

(2) Faris-Newton Without Mass Motion Equation

(3) Faris-Newton With mass Motion Laws Equation

(4) Faris-Newton Force Laws Equation

(5) Faris-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation

(6) Classical Mechanics

(4) Statements and Declarations

(A) Competing Interests

No, I declare that the authors have no competing interests or other interests that might be perceived to influence the results and/or discussion reported in this paper.

(B) Funding

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(C) Author Contribution

I am Mirza Faris Ahmad. The only Author and Researcher of this Research Paper.

(5)Faris'-Newton Classical Mechanics

(A)Introduction

First I will give prove of n Integrals of position function then I will generalize it into Faris-Newton Without Mass Motion Equation and Faris Newton With Mass Motion Laws Equation. The Faris-Newton Force Laws Equation which converts to Faris-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation is also following from mass one equation.

(B)Headings

1.Motion Laws

Defining N integrals of position function

Net distance covered (as defined by position function) integral with respect to any differential time is called movement.

Equation

$$M_1 = \int r(t) dt$$

Generalizing to n time integrals of position function.

$$M_n = \int \dots \int r(t) dt^n$$

Explanation

A body is moving and covering some displacement in a specific time interval in this way body's movement can be described and if a body covers some displacement then it can be represented by a position function. The displacement covered in differential time can also be referred to as movement then you have to take the integration for a long time interval.

Faris-Newton Without Mass Motion Equation

Consider a body is moving with uniform velocity and draw a displacement time graph. Consider the graph a straight line originating from a mid point in y axis of displacement and making elevation angle with horizontal. This graph is a hypotenuse of right angle triangle and below is the rectangle on which this right angled triangle is sitting. y increment of graph line is Δr and x increment of graph line is Δt .

First

The slope of the graph line is called velocity which is rise over run or y increment by x increment.

Equation

$$v = \frac{\Delta r}{\Delta t}$$

Second

The area of the triangle added in the area of the rectangle is the total area under the graph line named as total movement of an object.

Equation

$$M_1 = r_i t + \frac{1}{2} \Delta r t$$

Third

The area of a trapezoid is the total area under a graph line named as total movement of an object.

Equation

$$M_1 = \frac{r_f^2 - r_i^2}{2v}$$

Generalizing to n integrals of position function

The first equation is a simple condition that says velocity to be uniform and the other two equations are given for the total magnitude of movement under this condition generalizing both equations to integrals of position function gives the equation.

Equation

$$M_{n-1} = \int \dots \int M_1 dt^{n-1} = \int \dots \int (r_i t + \frac{1}{2} \Delta r t) dt^{n-1} \quad (1)$$

$$M_{n-1} = \int \dots \int M_1 dt^{n-1} = \int \dots \int \left(\frac{r_f^2 - r_i^2}{2v} \right) dt^{n-1} \quad (2)$$

Note:

More common in Physics are these position function time derivatives physical quantities called velocity, acceleration etc since they are already known. Consider the following Motion Equations also that does not include the n integrals of position function with respect to time but that are n position function time derivative.

$$\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left(\frac{v_f^2 - v_i^2}{2a} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \left(v_i t + \frac{1}{2} \Delta v t \right) \quad (4)$$

Combined

To combine all the four motion equations two about n integrals of position function named as (1) and (2) and the other two about the n derivatives of position function named as (3) and (4) into two the following equations are used.

Equation

$$D_t^n r(t) = D_t^n \left(v_i t + \frac{1}{2} \Delta v t \right)$$

$$D_t^n r(t) = D_t^n \left(\frac{v_f^2 - v_i^2}{2a} \right)$$

Note: The D is operator. When n=0 one will be left with only r(t) and positive n implies derivative of r(t) while negative n implies integral of r(t) but |n| in both positive and negative cases is the total number of integrals or derivatives and the positive or negative sign is just used to imply derivative or integral respectively. t is written to show that whenever there is integral or derivative it is with respect to t.

Faris-Newton With Mass Motion Laws Equation

Faris' Zeroth Law of with Mass Motion provides Mass source, Newton's First Law of with Mass Motion is Mass Motion physical explanation, Newton's Second Law of with Mass Motion is Mass Motion Mathematical Explanation and Newton's Third Law of with Mass Motion is a generalization to N Masses Motion. Mass Motion source along with its physical and mathematical Explanation along with its generalization to N Masses Motion is a complete explanation of With Mass Motion Laws named Faris-Newton With Mass Motion Laws. Faris' With Mass Motion Law (Zeroth) and Newton's With Mass Motion Laws (First, Second and Third) are combinely called Faris-Newton With Mass Motion Laws. The Combined With Mass Motion Laws equation is also made.

Equation

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_i (D_t^n r(t))_i = - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{E_j}{d_j}$$

Where E represents energy and left hand side must be written as T_m summation. Where $D_t^n r(t)$ is called T.T stands for Through and T_m

Stands for with Mass through.

Note:

1. To just clear the symbols a little bit the integral version of the above equation is like this:

Equation

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_i (\int \dots \int r(t) dt^n) = - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{(E_{M_j})}{d_j}$$

Where again on right hand side the double subscripted E is energy and left hand side can be written as M_m summation and $\int \dots \int r(t) dt^n$ can be written as M_n .

2. Faris-Newton with Mass Motion Laws Equation include n integral and derivatives of position function but the Faris-Newton with Mass Motion with n derivatives of position function Laws Equation has very great importance since for second time derivative it transforms to Faris-Newton Force Laws Equation which is mentioned after Faris-Newton Mass Motion with n derivatives of position function Laws Equation and this equation is:

Equation

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_i \left(\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t) \right) = - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{(E_{v_m_j})}{d_j}$$

Where again on right hand side the double subscripted E is energy and left hand side can be written as v_m summation and $\frac{d^n}{dt^n} r(t)$ can be written as v_n .

Faris-Newton Force Laws Equation

Faris' Zeroth Law of Force provides Force source, Newton's First Law of Force is Force physical explanation, Newton's Second Law of Force is Force Mathematical Explanation and Newton's Third Law of Force is a generalization to N forces. Force source along with its physical and mathematical Explanation and its generalization to N forces is a

complete explanation of Force Laws named as Faris-Newton Force Laws. Faris' Force Law (Zeroth) and Newton's Altered Force Laws (First, Second and Third) are combinedly called Faris-Newton Force Laws. The Combined Force Laws equation is also made.

Equation

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_i \left(\frac{d^2}{dt^2} r(t) \right)_i = - \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{U_j}{d_j}$$

2. Gravitation Force laws

Faris'-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation

Faris' Zeroth Law of Gravitation Force provides Gravitation Force source, Faris' First Law of Gravitation Force is physical explanation of Gravitation Force, Newton's Law of Gravitation is mathematical explanation of Gravitation Force and Faris' Second Law of Gravitation Force is a generalization to N Gravitation forces. Gravitation Force source along with the physical and mathematical explanation of Gravitation Force and its generalization to N Gravitation forces is a complete explanation of Gravitation Force Laws named Faris-Newton Gravitation Force Laws. Faris' Gravitation Force Laws (Zeroth, First and Second) and Newton's Gravitation Force Law are combinedly called Faris-Newton Gravitation Force Laws. The Combined Gravitation Force Laws equation is also made.

Equation

$$U = \frac{G d m_1 m_2}{d^2}$$

$$U = \frac{G d m_1 m_2 \left(r^3 \frac{dl}{dt} - r^2 a l - r a \frac{dl}{dt} + v a l \right)}{d^2 r^4 f}$$

(D) Importance

This Classical Mechanics is extremely important since it gives description about reality with its motion laws and gravitation force laws. I would not regard it as a third branch along with relativity and quantum mechanics but instead I would regard it as a sub-part of relativity as Newtonian mechanics is whose proof I will not give because I am regarding it a part of relativity rather than limits of relativity derive it. As relativity can describe about motion and gravitation of fluids also.

(E) Abbreviations

1. Faris-Newton With Mass Motion With n derivatives of position function Laws Equation, position function and Faris-Newton With Mass motion Equation with n Integrals of position function Laws Equation and Faris-Newton With mass Motion Laws Equation both refer to same thing.
2. Faris-Newton Without Mass motion Equation and Faris-Newton Motion Equation both refer to same thing.

(F)Prediction

Since the given things are already experimentally verified it is not difficult to understand. The moving object not only moves with multiple velocities (first, second, third, ...) but moving object has also multiple movements where the first means moving with respect to time and second means moving with time.

(G)Conclusion

Faris-Newton Classical Mechanics present Faris-Newton Without Mass Motion Equation which can be converted to Faris-Newton With Mass Motion Laws Equation which when specialized to Faris-Newton With Mass Motion with n derivatives of position function Laws Equation, position function and Faris-Newton With Mass Motion with n integrals of position function Laws Equation then the first with mass motion laws equation when obtained for second time derivative gives Faris-Newton Force Laws Equation that can be converted to Faris-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation.